

1 **Evaluation of anthropogenic air pollutant emission inventories for South America at**
2 **national and city scale**

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34

35 Abstract

36 The changing composition of the atmosphere, driven by anthropogenic emissions, is the
37 cause of anthropogenic climate change as well as deteriorating air quality. Emission
38 inventories are essential to understand the contribution of various human activities, model
39 and predict the changing atmospheric composition, and design cost-effective mitigation
40 measures. At present, national emission inventories in South America (SA) focus on
41 Greenhouse Gases (GHG) as part of their obligation to the United Nations Framework
42 Convention for Climate Change (UNFCCC) within the framework of their national
43 communications. Emission inventories other than GHG in SA focus mainly on growing
44 urban areas and megacities. Therefore, studies examining air quality at national, regional or
45 continental scales in SA depend on (down-scaled) global emission inventories. This paper
46 examines the emission estimates of air pollutants from various global inventories for five
47 SA countries, namely Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and Peru. A more detailed
48 analysis is conducted for the EDGAR and ECLIPSE emission inventories, in particular
49 comparing local city-scale inventories of a major city in each country. Although total
50 emissions between down-scaled global inventories and local city inventories are often
51 comparable, large discrepancies exist between the sectoral contributions. This is critical, as
52 the mitigation of poor air quality will depend on addressing the right sources. Potential
53 sources of discrepancies between global and local inventories include the spatial
54 distribution proxies, difference in emission factors used and/or the use of generic statistical
55 country data when estimating emissions. This highlights the importance of using local
56 information when generating national emission inventories, especially for air quality
57 modeling and development of effective mitigation measures. This study represents the first
58 step towards an increased understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of emissions
59 information in SA.

60 **Keywords;**

61 South America, anthropogenic emissions, air pollutants, Argentina, Brazil, Chile,
62 Colombia, Peru, city emission inventories

63 **1 Introduction and Rationale**

64 Over the last decades, environmental problems such as acidification, eutrophication,
65 air pollution and climate change have caused significant adverse impact on the
66 environment, human health and vegetation (Steffen et al, 2015; HTAP, 2010;
67 Schneidemesser et al., 2015). These environmental problems are directly related to the
68 atmospheric emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG), air pollutants and their precursors.
69 Reliable emission inventories are a prerequisite to understanding these environmental
70 issues, including the impact of anthropogenic activity on air quality and climate, and to
71 developing effective mitigation options. Furthermore, emission knowledge of GHG and air
72 pollutants are key in the development of integrated policies addressing climate change
73 and/or air quality (AQ) and reducing unintended consequences (Melamed et al., 2016;
74 Schmale et al., 2014; Reis et al., 2012).

75 South America is a continent spanning over the northern and southern hemisphere,
76 from the very cold Tierra del Fuego, close to Antarctica, to the equator and beyond to the
77 Caribbean Sea. Its climate exhibits tropical, subtropical, as well as extratropical features
78 (Garreaud et al., 2009). It includes the world's largest rainforest, considered the driest
79 desert outside polar regions (Rondanelli et al. 2015), and the Andes mountain range
80 peaking well above 6000 meters, introducing east-west climate asymmetries (Garreaud et
81 al., 2009). In short, it has a very diverse collection of ecosystems, physical landscapes and
82 climate zones. While SA countries experienced similar population growth in the last 20
83 years, there have been large differences in economic development. Emissions sources of air
84 pollutants dominating impact on air quality also vary largely from country to country, from
85 residential combustion in central and southern Chile (Saide et al., 2016; Mazzeo et al.,
86 2018) to transport in Colombia (Gonzalez et al., 2017; Pachon et al., 2018). Furthermore,
87 emission conditions also vary largely, in particular among main metropolitan areas; while
88 pollutants are emitted at sea level in Buenos Aires (Argentina), those in La Paz (Bolivia)
89 are emitted at approximately 3600 m above sea level. This altitude can have an important

90 impact on vehicle emissions with different emissions due to altitude (He et al., 2011; Ni et
91 al., 2014; Szedlmayer and Kweon, 2016; Wang et al., 2018).

92 Emission inventories developed in South American (SA) countries at a national level
93 typically focus on GHGs as part of the obligation of the Parties to the United Nations
94 Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) within the framework of their
95 national communications (Baumgardner et al., 2018). Emission inventories other than for
96 GHG in SA focus mainly on megacities in an effort to understand the interactions and
97 feedback mechanisms between emissions, AQ and public health (Alonso et al., 2010;
98 Gallardo et al., 2012a). Except for Argentina (Castesana et al., 2018; Puliafito et. Al.,
99 2015; 2017), no national emissions inventory for air pollutants is available with the spatial
100 and temporal detail needed for AQ modeling, analysis and policy support. Therefore, the
101 emission inventories currently used for national, regional or continental scale AQ
102 assessments in SA are derived from global data sets (e.g. Longo et al., 2013; Rosario et al.,
103 2013; Kumar et al., 2016; UNEP/CCAC, 2018).

104 The available global emission inventories for selected countries are analyzed by
105 source-sector in this paper. These countries are highly urbanized; with the exception of
106 Peru, urbanization is above 80% and more than 50% of the urban population of these
107 countries lives in cities with more than 300.000 inhabitants (UN, 2018). Air quality in the
108 SA cities is a major problem. Measurements of particulate matter of 2.5 microns or less
109 (PM_{2.5}) are available for 37 cities in these countries, 35 of them (representing
110 approximately 15% of SA population) experience annual average concentrations exceeding
111 the level recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017). Given the very
112 rates of urbanisation observed in South America (>80%), climate and air quality policies
113 can be better coordinated allowing for win-win options and attaining Sustainable
114 Development Goals (SDGs). Also, as urban CO₂ emissions become more and more
115 important in the global Budget, it is key to look for synergies in mitigation strategies aimed
116 at lowering the carbon footprint and exposure to air pollutants (e.g.,Anenberg et al, 2019)

117 This paper seeks to evaluate, give guidance and provide insight into the similarities
118 and differences among emission inventories for five selected SA countries, and possible
119 reasons for such discrepancies. Note that it is not within the scope of this work to provide a

120 full in-depth analysis of the emissions and underlying data used in various inventories, but
 121 rather provide an overview of SA inventories and document major differences that users of
 122 such inventories (e.g. modeling studies) should consider. Furthermore, this analysis focuses
 123 foremost on air pollutants, many of which also act as climate forcers (CCA-UNEP, 2018).
 124 Both the global and local emission inventories for selected cities in the five SA countries,
 125 as well as the sources considered, are presented in section 2. Sections 3 and 4 present a
 126 comparative analysis of the estimated emissions between the five countries investigating
 127 the reasons for discrepancies. Discussion of main results is presented in section 5, followed
 128 by conclusions in section 6.

129

130 2 Methods and data

131 2.1 General country information and data

132 South America has an area of 17,840,000 km² and its 2010 population is estimated at
 133 416 Million (UN PD, 2018) (**Table 1**). The five countries selected for available emissions
 134 data analysis in this study are Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and Peru. They cover
 135 80% of the land area and 84% of the population of South America (**Table 1**).

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Country	ISO3 code	Area (km ²) ^{a)}	Total Population (10 ⁶) ^{b)}	Urban Population [%] ^{b)}
Argentina	ARG	2736690	43.4	92
Brazil	BRA	8459420	206	86
Chile	CHL	743800	17.8	87
Colombia	COL	1109500	48.2	80
Peru	PER	1280000	31.4	77
Sum of 5 countries		14329410	346.7	86
Total	South America	17840000	416.4	84

137 **Table 1:** Selected generic data of the selected five countries in South America

138 ^{a)} Source FAOstat accessed through <https://unstats.un.org/>

139 ^{b)} UN PD (2018)

140

141 The population of the selected countries is estimated at 330 million in 2010. The
 142 demographic development of the countries is similar, in all five countries the population
 143 has doubled since 1970. When we focus on the last 20 years (1995-2015), the population
 144 has grown by about 30% and again the pattern for the 5 countries is similar. The
 145 development in gross domestic product (GDP), however, has been less similar and less
 146 gradual (Figure 1). Since Brazil is by far the largest country, its GDP follows the average
 147 rather closely but Colombia and Peru are clearly below the average, while Chile and
 148 Argentina are above the average. Moreover, while the GDP for Chile has mostly increased
 149 since the beginning of the 1980's, Argentina experienced a decrease in GDP from 1998
 150 until 2003, and Peru generally shows an increase in the last decade. A common feature for
 151 all SA countries is the pervasive inequity (e.g., Amarante et al, 2016), which is also
 152 relevant when considering consumption, emissions and exposure patterns (e.g., Gallardo et
 153 al, 2012b; Carpenter and Quispe-Agnoli, 2015).

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 156 **Figure 1:** Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita (\$US/capita in constant 2010 prices)
 157 for the same five selected countries in SA. The GDP corresponding to Latin America and
 158 the Caribbean is also included.

159

160 **2.2 Global emission data**

161 Emission inventories providing data for SA countries from 1970 to present are collected
162 and compared for the pollutants of primary concern: nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide
163 (SO₂), Black Carbon (BC), particulate Organic Carbon (OC), particulate matter of 10
164 microns or less (PM₁₀), particulate matter of 2.5 microns or less (PM_{2.5}), carbon monoxide
165 (CO), and ammonia (NH₃). Methane (CH₄) is important in atmospheric chemistry (e.g.,
166 ozone formation at the regional and hemispheric scales) but this tracer is explicitly included
167 in the GHG emission inventories and is therefore not discussed in this study. A comparison
168 of the data from the various inventories by pollutant and by country for the time period of
169 1970 to 2010 is provided in section 3.1.

170

171 Although the total number of (global) emission inventories that provide information on SA
172 is substantial (**Table 2**), a more in-depth analysis is made for a selection of recent
173 inventories. The selection of inventories is based on:

- 174 1. Inventories need to include the recent period 2000-2010 for comparison with other local
175 data sources such as SA city inventories
- 176 2. From every “family” of EIs we take the latest version at the start of our investigation;
177 e.g., we look in detail at EDGAR 4.3 and not version 4.2.
- 178 3. The inventory needs to have sectorial emission information.

179

180 Based on these criteria, our further analysis focuses on EDGAR 4.3.1, ECLIPSE v5a,
181 CEDSV3 and MACCity. The MACCity inventory for the years after 2000 is a projection
182 based on the RCP8.5 projection by Riahi et al. (2007). As it was used in several studies in
183 support of IPCC AR5 analysis, we include it for reference but will not analyze the implied
184 emission factors or discrepancies in trends compared to the other bottom-up inventories. A
185 brief introduction to the selected inventories is provided below; refer to the provided
186 references for more details. The emission inventories are accessible through the ECCAD
187 server (<https://eccad.aeris-data.fr/>)

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Acronym	Perio	Reference and/or website
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	d	
MACCity	1980-2010	Granier et al., 2011 http://eccad.aeris-data.fr/
ACCMIP	1980-2010	Lamarque et al., 2010 http://eccad.aeris-data.fr/
RCPs	2000-2010	Van Vuuren et al., 2011 http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web-apps/tnt/RcpDb
EDGAR v4.2	1970-2008	Janssens-Maenhout et al., 2013 http://edgar.jrc.europa.eu/
EDGAR v4.3.1	1970 and 2010	Crippa et al., 2016 http://edgar.jrc.europa.eu/os
HTAPv2	2008 and 2010	Janssens-Maenhout et al., 2015 http://edgar.jrc.europa.eu/htap_v2
ECLIPSE v4a	2005-2010	Stohl et al., 2015 http://eclipse.nilu.no http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchPrograms/air/ECLIPSEv4a.html
ECLIPSE v5	1990-2010	Klimont et al., 2017 http://eclipse.nilu.no http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchPrograms/air/ECLIPSEv5a.html
Junker&Liouss	1860-1997	Junker and Liouss, 2008
PKU	2002-2013	Huang et al., 2014 http://inventory.pku.edu.cn
CEDS	1950-2014	Hoesly et al., 2018 http://www.globalchange.umd.edu/ceds/

190 **Table 2:** Overview of selected global emission data sets containing data for anthropogenic emissions for
191 South America.
192

193 2.2.1 EDGAR v4.3.1 (January 2016)

194 The Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) provides global
195 historic anthropogenic emissions of GHG and air pollutants by country and sector. EDGAR
196 uses a bottom-up methodology with international activity data and emission factors
197 (Janssens-Maenhout et al., 2017; Crippa et al., 2018). The estimated national emissions by
198 sector are distributed on a 0.1°x0.1° grid using geospatial proxy data. In EDGARv4.3.1
199 emissions are calculated for gaseous and particulate air pollutants per sector and country for
200 the time series 1970-2010. Version v4.3.1 is the official release of the EDGAR database
201 used for PEGASOS scenarios (Crippa et al., 2016). Source sector specification follows the
202 IPCC 1996 code, as was also done for EDGAR v4.2.

203

204 2.2.2 ECLIPSEv5a

205 The ECLIPSE emission data set was created with the GAINS (Greenhouse gas – Air
206 pollution Interactions and Synergies; <http://gains.iiasa.ac.at>) model (Amann et al., 2011),
207 which calculates emissions of air pollutants and Kyoto greenhouse gases in a consistent
208 framework. The GAINS model holds essential information about key sources of emissions,
209 environmental policies, and further mitigation opportunities for 170 country-regions. The
210 model relies on national and international statistics of activity data for energy use, industrial
211 production, and agricultural activities for which it distinguishes key emission sources and
212 related control measures. Several hundred technologies to control air pollutant and
213 greenhouse gas emissions are represented allowing simulation of implemented air quality
214 legislation. Recently the regional resolution of the global GAINS model has been improved
215 by distinguishing more countries in Latin America, as five regions were replaced with 13
216 regions in version V5a, including most countries of South America (UNEP/CCAC. 2018).
217 For more details we refer to Klimont et al. (2017).

218

219 2.2.3 CEDSV3 (as of March 2017)

220 The Community Emissions Database System (CEDSV) is an open source data system that
221 produces global, historical (1750 - present) estimates of anthropogenic acidifying gases
222 (Hoesly et al., 2018). Emissions are estimated annually and resolved by country, sector, and
223 fuel, and then gridded by year and sector with monthly seasonality. CEDSV estimates rely on
224 existing energy consumption data sets and regional and country-specific inventories to
225 produce emission trends over recent decades. A historical emissions dataset was released in
226 2016 for use in research, including CMIP6. For more detailed information see
227 www.globalchange.umd.edu/CEDSV

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229 2.2.4 MACCity

230 The MACCity emissions dataset is based on the ACCMIP (Atmospheric Chemistry and
231 Climate - Model Intercomparison Project) historical emissions dataset developed by
232 Lamarque et al. (2010) and combined with the IPCC AR5 future emissions scenarios called
233 RCPs (Representation Concentration Pathways, Van Vuuren et al., 2011). The ACCMIP

234 and the RCPs emissions dataset have been adapted and extended on a yearly basis for the
 235 period 1990-2010. Anthropogenic emissions were interpolated on a yearly basis between
 236 the base years 1990, 2000, 2005 and 2010. For the years 2005 and 2010, the RCP 8.5
 237 emissions scenario was chosen. For biomass burning emissions, the ACCMIP dataset was
 238 also extended on a monthly basis. Best reference to the data set is Lamarque et al (2010).

239

240 2.3 City emission data in South America

241 Local emission inventories are compiled for megacities in South America to address
 242 deteriorated air quality and implement measures to reduce the concentration of air
 243 pollutants in these cities (D’Angiola et al., 2010; Gallardo et al., 2012a).

244 For each of the five countries, one city was selected to evaluate the local inventory
 245 against emissions from downscaled global inventories. A city inventory contains the
 246 emissions occurring within the territory of the city (Table 3) and therefore the
 247 corresponding emissions from global inventories are extracted based on the squared area
 248 surrounding each city. To assess the impact of the choice of the area surrounding the city,
 249 two domains are considered when extracting the city emissions from global inventories; a
 250 small relatively tight domain following the city limits and a somewhat larger one to test if
 251 potential sources that in fact belong to the city are not included in the smaller domain. This
 252 method is rather crude and may introduce errors in the estimate, which are discussed in
 253 section 4.

254

City	Country	Year (s)	Sectors	Pollutants	Reference
Buenos Aires	Argentina	1970-2012	Transport	PM ₁₀ , NO _x , SO ₂ , CO, VOC	D’Angiola, et al., 2010
Bogota	Colombia	2012	Transport & Industry	PM ₁₀ , NO _x , SO _x , CO, CO ₂ , VOC	Rojas & Peñalosa, 2012; Pachón et al., 2018
Lima	Peru	2014	Transport, Residential, Industry	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO _x , SO _x , CO, CO ₂ , VOC	Reátegui et al., 2018

Santiago	Chile	2012	Transport, Industry, Residential, Agriculture, Construction, Total	PM2.5, PM ₁₀ , NO _x , SO _x , CO, CO ₂ , VOC, CH ₄ , NH ₃	USACH, 2014
Rio de Janeiro	Brazil	2013	Transport	TSP, NO _x , SO _x , CO	GQA, 2016

255 **Table 3:** Overview of cities data (city, year(s), pollutants, reference) – see section 3.1
256

257 2.4 Source sector definitions

258 The global inventories used in this paper have different source-sector definitions.
259 Therefore, we have aggregated several sectors creating categories that allow for comparison
260 of the inventories (**Table 4**). The individual inventories have a far more detailed sector
261 breakdown than we use here. For example, EDGAR provides emission data for 12 IPCC
262 1996 main source categories whereas we aggregate the data into 8 different sectors.
263

<i>Source sector</i>	Description
Agriculture	Livestock and crop production, including open burning of agricultural residues
Power	Power generation, transformation industry and refineries
Industry	Combustion and process emissions from industry
FF_prod	Fossil Fuel exploration, processing and distribution
Residential	Household cooking and heating, and small commercial stationary
Combustion	combustion
Waste	Solid waste disposal and waste incineration (without energy/heat recovery)
Transportation	Road and non-road transport; excluding international shipping and international non-LTO ^{a)} aviation
Solvents	Use of solvents

264 **Table 4:** The aggregated source sectors used for comparison of selected inventories and city inventories. Note
265 that in this study, Agriculture does not include savanna burning, but does include agricultural waste burning.
266 Furthermore, CEDS includes agriculture waste burning under Waste – not under agriculture; ECLIPSE
267 includes emissions from flaring in oil and gas industry (FF_prod).
268 ^{a)} Landing and take off

269 3 Results

270 3.1 Emission inventories by pollutant and by country

271 The SO₂ and BC emissions from the different global emission inventories (**Table 2**) for the
272 five SA countries are plotted as a function of time (Fig 2, Fig 3, respectively). Similar
273 figures for other pollutants are presented in supplement material (Figures S01 to S06). The
274 main observation is that emission estimates from different inventories vary widely and do
275 not show a trend to converge. For some countries, the early years vary widely (e.g.
276 Argentina SO₂), while for others the discrepancy increases with time (e.g. Peru SO₂).
277 Overall, discrepancies of a factor 2-3 are present for all countries and pollutants. Some of
278 the inventories shown in **Table 2** and Fig 2 and Fig. 3 are no longer considered up to date
279 but the overview is useful because these inventories were used in important global
280 assessments and it is likely that those results are sensitive to such differences in emissions
281 data. We will not discuss all these discrepancies in detail, since differences are not only
282 inventory specific but also species and country specific. Therefore, no structural
283 overarching explanation exists but more a long list of rather anecdotal justifications. It is
284 not the aim of this study to provide a long list of individual clarifications. To illustrate this
285 point, and the complexities underlying these differences, the discrepancies in SO₂
286 emissions for Peru are discussed in detail in the Supplemental Information (SI section 1.3).
287 In general, discrepancies between the emission inventories are multiple and include:

- 288 1. Emission factors may have been updated and improved over time.
- 289 2. Activity data may have been updated and improved over time.
- 290 3. New sources may have been identified over time.
- 291 4. The definition of sources to be included in the inventory may differ between
292 inventories.
- 293 5. Assumptions about the implementation of pollution control policies over time may
294 differ across the inventories.
- 295 6. Since some inventories are not developed at a country level, the spatial distribution
296 proxies for key sources might strongly influence results, e.g., all RCPs, ECLIPSEv4a
- 297 7. Global inventories may combine different sources of information and origin for
298 different pollutants.

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Figure 2: Total annual sulphur dioxide (SO₂) emissions [Tg/yr] for the period 1970 to 2010 for global emission inventories: MACCity, EDGARv2, EDGARv3, HTAPv2, ECLIPSEv4a, ECLIPSEv5a, RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6, RCP8.5, CEDSV1, CEDSV2 and CEDSV3. See legend for colors and symbols associated to each inventory.

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Figure 3: Same as Figure 2 but for black carbon (BC) and global inventories: MACCity, PKU, Junker-Liousse, HTAPv2, ECLIPSEv4, ECLIPSEv5, RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6, RCP8.5, EDGARv3 and CEDSv3.

310 Based on the criteria outlined in section 2.3 we focus further analysis on four recent
311 emission inventories; EDGAR 4.3.1, ECLIPSEv5a, CEDSv3 and MACCity and restrict the
312 analysis to the years 1995 to 2010. Subsequent versions of emission inventories can differ
313 substantially due to some of the reasons outlined above. Compare for example ECLIPSE
314 v4a and v5a; CEDSv1 and v3 in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Klimont et al. (2017) document that
315 the major change between their ECLIPSE v5a and previous ECLIPSE versions is that IEA
316 and FAO statistical data were reimported for the period 1990-2010, international shipping
317 was included, that their global BC numbers are higher than previously published owing
318 primarily to the inclusion of new sources, and spatial resolution was improved to
319 distinguish all single countries in SA. Another often-overlooked issue, is the inclusion or
320 exclusion of semi-anthropogenic sources like forest fires or agricultural waste burning.
321 Compare for example HTAPv2.2 and EDGARv4.3.1 in Figure 3 for Brazil. The emissions
322 for all source sectors are equal but HTAPv2.2 excludes agricultural waste burning, and
323 EDGARv4.3 includes it. In SA this is a relevant source and therefore HTAPv2.2 and
324 EDGARv4.3.1 appear as different inventories but the difference is simply a result of
325 inclusion or exclusion of agricultural waste burning. Out of simplicity, the version of each
326 inventory will be omitted henceforth and inventories will be referred to as EDGAR,
327 ECLIPSE and CEDS.

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Figure 4: Total annual emissions of SO₂ (left), BC (center) and NO_x (right) [Tg/yr] for global inventories MACCity (green), EDGAR4.3 (black), ECLIPSEv5a (red) and CEDSV3 (blue) for the period 1995 to 2010.

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It is also important to note that emission inventories may show comparable patterns for one country and significantly diverse patterns for another country. Differences are seen in terms of trend and/or magnitude and this is mostly related to different key source

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336 contributions in different countries. For SO₂ these differences are seen both in terms of
337 trends for Argentina and magnitude for Colombia and Peru (Figure 4). Whereas for NO_x
338 and BC, differences are mostly in terms of magnitude; see for example Argentina and
339 Colombia for NO_x and Brazil and Chile for BC (Figure 4) (See figures S7 to S10 for
340 equivalent figures of the other pollutants considered in this study). We highlight that for
341 most species the SA year-to-year variability (lower panels) is dominated by emissions in
342 Brazil except for SO₂ and NO_x. For SO₂ annual variability is also determined by emissions
343 in Chile and Peru resulting from their mining activities. Argentina also contributes to the
344 SA year-to-year variability for NO_x emissions.

345 In addition to the spread in total emissions presented above, the EIs also differ in the
346 relative contribution of each sector (Table S1 in the supplement material). While the
347 diversity between the emission inventories is small for SO₂ and NH₃ it is considerable for
348 the other species. A more detailed description of this diversity in sectorial emissions
349 between inventories is provided in the supplemental material.

350

351 3.2 Particulate matter emissions

352 Particulate matter and its components, BC and OC are important species for air quality,
353 health and climate change (Bond et al, 2013; IPCC, 2018). In addition to BC and OC,
354 primary PM emissions can also include other components such as sulphates, metals, salts
355 and mineral particles but in combustion emissions the bulk is BC + OC. Therefore, looking
356 at BC+OC in relation to PM provides information on the type of emission factors used.
357 Moreover, theoretically BC+OC cannot exceed PM_{2.5} as BC and OC emissions are in
358 general smaller than 2.5 μm, except for some source signatures like poorly operated two-
359 stroke engines where OC can be larger than PM_{2.5}. The contribution of BC and BC+OC to
360 PM_{2.5} as well as the contribution of PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ is analyzed in more detail in Table 5. In
361 addition, we pay attention to the ratio of CO to NO_x (Table 5), which may provide insights
362 into the role of traffic emissions (Monks et al, 2015; Gallardo et al, 2012b; Vivanco and
363 Andrade, 2006). Note that the present analysis and Table 5 are only for Transport
364 emissions.

365 EDGAR in general has larger BC content in PM_{2.5} than ECLIPSE, except for Chile. In
366 both inventories this contribution increases from 1995 to 2010, except for Argentina, and

367 this increase is larger in ECLIPSE than EDGAR. Although BC is the product of incomplete
368 combustion, such a trend can be explained by better combustion at higher temperatures,
369 which first causes less particulate OC formation, and in a later, further advanced stage may
370 also reduce the formation of BC. For the fraction of BC+OC in PM_{2.5}, EDGAR presents the
371 same features as for BC; decreasing trend in Argentina and increasing in the other countries
372 with the largest increase in Chile. This similarity between both ratios is likely due to the use
373 of the same drivers to estimate the emissions. However, in ECLIPSE the country with the
374 largest growth in BC/PM_{2.5} ratio was Colombia, whereas for the ratio (BC + OC)/PM_{2.5}
375 Chile and Peru presented the largest increase. A possible reason for this different pace of
376 change in these ratios is that the structure of sectors changes over time and implementation
377 of policies affects this as well since the efficiency of removing BC/OC/PM is different for
378 each technology. We note that both Argentina and Peru have unrealistic fractions larger
379 than 1 in EDGAR (Table 5)¹ The use of independent OC emission factors in EDGAR (that
380 is, independent from PM_{2.5}) could explain these unrealistic values and allow BC+OC to be
381 larger than PM_{2.5}. In addition, EDGAR considers that all emitted PM₁₀ for road transport is
382 also PM_{2.5} while ECLIPSE estimates the coarse PM fraction (PM₁₀-PM_{2.5}) to be
383 approximately 10%, and gradually increasing over time from approximately 8% to 11%.
384 Finally, the CO/NO_x ratio decreases over time with a comparable decrease in both
385 inventories. When comparing the ratios CO/NO_x by country and across the years we see a
386 consistent lower CO/NO_x ratio for ECLIPSE to EDGAR. Yet, while in EDGAR, both
387 Argentina and Chile show an increasing trend since 2005, in ECLIPSE only Chile presents
388 this trend. The CO/NO_x emission ratios are important for atmospheric chemistry and
389 composition. If better national data were available, this discrepancy should be analyzed and
390 reconciled or at least better understood as it highlights a fundamental difference.

391

392

393

394

¹ This is now corrected in version EDGARv4.3.2 where the PM_{2.5}biofuel, PM_{2.5}fossil and BC and OC have been revised and a ratio smaller than 1 is guaranteed for the sum of BC and OC over the sum of PM_{2.5}fossil and PM_{2.5}biofuel.

Transp.	EDGAR4.3.1-Ref			ECLIPSEv5			EDGAR4.3.1	ECLIPSEv
	BC/PM2.5	(BC+OC)/PM2.5	PM2.5/PM10	BC/PM2.5	(BC+OC)/PM2.5	PM2.5/PM10	-Ref	5
1995							CO/NOx	CO/NOx
Argentina	0.71	1.18	1.00	0.45	0.82	0.94	14.28	5.51
Brazil	0.52	0.86	1.00	0.45	0.82	0.93	9.57	6.31
Chile	0.38	0.63	1.00	0.44	0.84	0.91	16.77	7.76
Colombia	0.48	0.80	1.00	0.20	0.78	0.91	28.71	12.26
Peru	0.65	1.08	1.00	0.36	0.81	0.92	12.57	5.88
2000								
Argentina	0.69	1.14	1.00	0.48	0.84	0.94	9.70	4.01
Brazil	0.53	0.89	1.00	0.48	0.84	0.92	8.86	5.51
Chile	0.51	0.81	1.00	0.48	0.87	0.90	17.87	6.76
Colombia	0.48	0.79	1.00	0.33	0.80	0.89	23.14	10.17
Peru	0.63	1.04	1.00	0.44	0.85	0.92	10.43	5.46
2005								
Argentina	0.67	1.09	1.00	0.50	0.83	0.93	8.16	3.28
Brazil	0.50	0.83	1.00	0.50	0.84	0.91	7.22	4.81
Chile	0.46	0.73	1.00	0.54	0.90	0.89	11.36	5.08
Colombia	0.52	0.84	1.00	0.39	0.81	0.89	17.66	8.13
Peru	0.71	1.15	1.00	0.48	0.86	0.91	9.27	4.55
2010								
Argentina	0.69	1.13	1.00	0.53	0.85	0.92	13.02	3.13
Brazil	0.54	0.88	1.00	0.53	0.87	0.90	6.11	3.56
Chile	0.50	0.79	1.00	0.57	0.93	0.86	12.01	5.42
Colombia	0.52	0.84	1.00	0.46	0.82	0.89	11.51	5.88
Peru	0.84	1.32	1.00	0.51	0.88	0.89	7.52	3.74

395 **Table 5:** Road transport emission fraction of BC in PM_{2.5}, BC+OC in PM_{2.5}, fraction of PM_{2.5} in PM₁₀
396 and CO/NO_x ratio for EDGAR and ECLIPSE.
397 Note: the color scale only applies to CO/NO_x as shown, it becomes lighter from 1995 to 2010 and that
398 EDGAR CO/NO_x ratio tends to be higher than ECLIPSE
399

400 3.3 Comparison of city emission data with global inventories

401 Emission estimates from local and global inventories are intercompared for total
402 emission as well as individual source sectors (Transport, Industry and Residential)
403 whenever available. To keep the comparison transparent, only EDGAR and ECLIPSE are
404 considered in this analysis because CEDS partly relies on EDGAR and other inventories.
405 One city per country was selected; namely Bogota, Buenos Aires, Lima, Rio de Janeiro and
406 Santiago (Table 3). Unfortunately, the local city inventories differ substantially in terms of
407 sectors included, period and pollutants considered (Table 3). Furthermore, while both
408 global EIs are available for the year 2010, the local city EIs are only available for specific
409 years and the year nearest to 2010 was selected (Table 3). In addition, while global EIs rely
410 mostly on international activity data to estimate emissions, local city EIs exclusively use
411 local databases not necessarily consistently integrated in the international datasets. The
412 corresponding emissions from the global EIs for a given city were derived by considering
413 emissions within a squared domain surrounding the city. To assess the sensitivity of the
414 method, two domains are considered; a small one with its limits in the vicinity of the city
415 and a larger one considering potential sources excluded in the smaller domain. Maps
416 illustrating each domain as well as the emissions included in each one are provided in the
417 supplemental material (Figure S11 to S13).

418 The total emissions from Santiago and Buenos Aires (the only two cities with
419 emission estimates for all sectors) will be analyzed first and then the analysis will be
420 extended to sectorial emissions for the remaining cities. We focus on two pollutants; NO_x
421 and PM₁₀, since the goal of this analysis is not to validate either inventory but to highlight
422 differences in magnitude between them and identify the impact of local information in the
423 estimate. In Table 6 an overview is given for the cutout from EDGAR and ECLIPSE that
424 represents the Santiago and Buenos Aires metropolitan areas by sector and how it relates to
425 national total emissions. Knowing that over 1/3 of Argentina's and Chile's population live
426 in their corresponding capitals (Buenos Aires and Santiago, respectively) their share of
427 Transport emissions appears small but an in-depth analysis by inventory would be needed

428 to fully understand this. Furthermore, regardless of the domain considered, ECLIPSE
429 attributes a larger fraction of the total national transport emissions to both cities than
430 EDGAR while the opposite occurs for industrial emissions. For residential and total
431 emissions, percentages between both inventories and for both domains are comparable. In
432 terms of NO_x emissions, for Buenos Aires both inventories assign comparable percentages
433 of the total emissions to transport but differ for residential and industrial emissions. In spite
434 of these differences, both inventories allocate comparable fractions of the national total
435 emissions to Buenos Aires. On the contrary, for Santiago both inventories present
436 comparable percentages for transport and industrial emissions but differ in residential and
437 total emissions. Detailed, spatial explicit national inventories for Argentina and Chile
438 would be extremely useful to elucidate the reasons for the discrepancies highlighted above.
439 For EDGAR the geospatial proxy data have been disclosed in Janssens-Maenhout et al.
440 (2017) for the sake of transparency but exactly why higher or lower shares of emissions are
441 attributed to the city remains unclear.

442 The relative magnitude of total NO_x emissions for both cities depends on the domain
443 or regions considered to estimate the city emissions from global inventories. For Buenos
444 Aires, EDGAR presents comparable emissions to the local inventory when the smaller
445 domain is considered and larger emissions when using the larger domain, whereas the
446 contrary is observed for Santiago where the estimate based on the larger domain is
447 comparable to the local inventory and the one based on the smaller domain presents smaller
448 emissions than the local one (Figure 5). Spatial distribution of the emissions in each city
449 explains this opposite behavior; while for Buenos Aires most of the city NO_x emissions are
450 distributed within the city domain enclosed by the smaller domain, for Santiago the
451 emissions are distributed beyond the city limits and thus fall outside of the smaller domain
452 but are captured by the larger one (Figure 6, see also Figures S13 and S14 in the
453 supplement material same figures for other cities and PM_{2.5}). For Santiago, contrary to
454 EDGAR, ECLIPSE presents larger emissions than the local inventory regardless of the
455 domain used to estimate the city emissions. For Buenos Aires however, the estimate based
456 on the larger domain is comparable to the local inventory while the estimate based on the
457 smaller domain is smaller than the local inventory. The local inventories in both cities
458 estimate smaller emissions for the Transport sector (Figure 5). The contrasting estimates

459 between the Transport sector and the Residential and Industrial sectors between the Global
 460 EIs and the local city EIs may be partly related to the distribution proxies used in the global
 461 inventories but the impact on total emissions attributed to the cities is large (Figure 5).

462 Except for Transport, both EIs (and regardless of the domain used to estimate the city
 463 emissions) present larger PM10 emissions than local inventories for both cities. Finally, for
 464 total emissions both inventories present comparable emissions for Buenos Aires whereas
 465 for Santiago EDGAR presents larger emissions than ECLIPSE per domain.

466

467 **Figure 5:** Total and sector emissions (Transport, Residential and Industry) of NOx
 468 and PM10 for Buenos Aires (a and b, respectively) and Santiago (c and d, respectively) for
 469 local EIs (blue) as well as global EIs EDGAR (red) and ECLIPSE (green). Estimates for
 470 large (filled) and small (shaded) domain are included for each global EI. See SI figure S01
 471 for limits of each domain and city boundaries.
 472

473 The analysis is extended to all selected cities for the Industrial, Residential and
 474 Transport sector. Emissions from both global inventories are presented only when a local
 475 inventory is available for comparison (Figure S15 in supplement material). The analysis
 476 focuses on cities not analyzed before, namely Bogota and Lima. Residential and Industrial

477 emissions present the same features for both pollutants; global inventories are mostly larger
 478 than the local ones. While in general EDGAR emissions are larger than those of ECLIPSE
 479 for both sectors in Bogota, the opposite is seen for Lima where ECLIPSE is larger than
 480 EDGAR. We note that for Lima, estimates for each inventory between both approaches are
 481 mostly the same indicating that allocation of the sources are confined within the city
 482 included in the smaller domain. The opposite of Residential and Industrial emissions is
 483 seen in the Transport sector for NO_x where the local inventories are mostly larger than the
 484 global ones (probably due to the geospatial allocation of roads times population into the
 485 city). The exception to this is Rio de Janeiro where based on the domain considered for the
 486 estimate the estimates are either larger (EDGAR based no large domain), smaller
 487 (ECLIPSE based on small domain) or comparable to the local inventory. For PM₁₀
 488 emissions from the Transport sector, EDGAR mostly estimates smaller emissions than the
 489 local inventory whereas ECLIPSE in general estimates larger emissions with the exception
 490 of Lima where they are comparable with the local inventory.
 491

492 **Figure 6:** Annual ECLIPSE (left column) and EDGAR (middle column) NO_x emissions
 493 for Buenos Aires (top row) and Santiago (bottom row). Note that the spatial scale is not the
 494 same for ECLIPSE and EDGAR. Corresponding maps for each city are included on the
 495 right column, where large (continuous red line) and small (dashed red line) regions
 496 considered to estimate the city emission from each EI are also included.

497
 498 Although the magnitude of the estimated emissions from the global inventories for
 499 each city depends on the region considered, the results with respect to the local inventories
 500 are, in general, independent of the selected domain.

501

	EDGAR				ECLIPSE			
	Transport	RCO	Industry	All sectors	Transport	RCO	Industry	All sectors
PM10								
(tons/yr)								
Buenos Aires	580 (868)	2491 (3192)	12643 (13424)	31020 (36836)	11805 (13943)	5146 (6295)	3553 (4647)	28655 (36814)
Percentage of national total	6% (8%)	26% (33%)	28% (30%)	8% (9%)	24% (29%)	31% (38%)	8% (11%)	11% (15%)
Santiago	618 (751)	28976 (36834)	13170 (15989)	60396 (74994)	3994 (5842)	21635 (36640)	5398 (8182)	39611 (62920)
Percentage of national total	4% (5%)	31% (39%)	38% (47%)	25% (31%)	27% (39%)	25% (43%)	10% (15%)	21% (34%)
NO_x								
(tons/yr)								
Buenos Aires	19386 (28285)	16664 (18545)	64053 (68106)	137160 (161879)	38348 (47182)	8760 (10442)	35508 (41205)	116671 (138942)
Percentage of national total	10% (15%)	68% (75%)	75% (80%)	29% (34%)	12% (14%)	45% (54%)	51% (59%)	23% (28%)
Santiago	13125 (15299)	4420 (5564)	15398 (18769)	40774 (49008)	12005 (16360)	3644 (6546)	48420 (52740)	80195 (94801)
Percentage of national total	13% (15%)	51% (64)%	47% (57%)	17% (21)%	9% (13%)	39% (70%)	53% (58%)	30% (35%)

502 **Table 6:** Extracted city domain emissions of small (large) domain for Buenos Aires and Santiago for PM10
 503 and NO_x in 2010 and the fraction of national total emissions located in the city domain for 2010
 504

505 4 Discussion.

506 Brazil is the largest emitter of all analyzed species, except for SO₂ where its
 507 emissions are comparable with those from Chile and Peru. This is not surprising as it is the

508 largest and most populated country in SA. However, when emissions are considered per
509 capita, i.e. they are normalized by population, Brazil's domination disappears (Figure 7 and
510 8). To limit the amount of data, we only present normalized data for the inventories
511 ECLIPSE and EDGAR, including more inventories would not provide significantly
512 different insights. We only normalize sectors by population if population has a direct link
513 with activities causing emissions, such as heating of houses (residential), commuting
514 (transport) and industrial heat/power usage. For sectors like agriculture and industry,
515 population is not a good proxy to normalize emissions. Normalization by population of
516 EDGAR emissions reveals that Chile is, in general, the country with the largest emissions
517 per capita among these five countries. Chile stands out as the largest emitter per capita for
518 SO₂, PM₁₀ and OC mostly related to the residential sector and power generation (Figure 6).
519 For BC, Chile also dominates due to transport and residential emissions. Finally, emissions
520 of CO and NO_x are dominated by the transport sector where again Chile has the largest
521 emissions per capita, however, those from Argentina and Brazil follow with smaller
522 differences than for the other species. Normalization of ECLIPSE emissions by population
523 presents similar figures as EDGAR for the power and residential sector with larger implied
524 emission factors (EF) for EDGAR in the power sector but, in general, smaller ones in the
525 residential sector (Figure 8). The largest differences between both inventories are seen in
526 the transport sector. While Chile is the largest emitter per capita for PM₁₀, BC, OC and NO_x
527 according to EDGAR, the largest emitter according to ECLIPSE is Argentina. Part of the
528 differences can be understood from geographical data. Chile is the country with a
529 substantial amount of the population living in the South with cold winters and residential
530 emission will be much higher in a cold climate, hence higher per capita emissions for the
531 residential sector. Another explaining factor is the economic development, in a relatively
532 affluent country like Chile (see Fig 1) more people will own a car or have access to
533 transportation and as a result more vehicle km (vkm) and transport emissions per person
534 can be expected. This, however, already becomes more difficult to generalize because a
535 more affluent country will have a more modern car fleet with less emissions per vkm, but
536 more vkm still creates more emissions. So, while per capita transport emissions in Chile
537 rank high (Figure 7 and 8), per vkm they would probably be lower than some of the other
538 countries. The data for power is the most difficult to interpret. For SO₂ it is related to the S

539 content in the fuel used but more importantly we may have to correct for (small) industrial
 540 power use and we lack the data to properly do this. Also, climatic differences may play a
 541 role. In general, the normalization in Figure 7 and 8 suggests we may expect that per capita
 542 emissions from Colombia and Peru will still grow.
 543

544
 545 **Figure 7:** Normalized (by population) national emissions of SO₂, CO, PM₁₀, BC,
 546 NO_x and OC from the global inventory EDGAR for Transport (yellow), RCO (green) and
 547 Power (blue) sector for the five selected countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and
 548 Peru).

549

550 Global Inventories use generic statistical country data to estimate emissions by
551 combining, for example, transportation fuel sales data with emissions factors (e.g. Klimont
552 et al. 2017, Crippa et al., 2018). Using road transport as an example, it is known that the
553 emission factors are strongly dependent on the engine technology, type of fuel and fuel
554 quality. The latter is highly variable and rapidly changing in SA. Global scale inventories
555 try to capture this change over time but can only do so in a rather generic way, at best for
556 individual countries but often by grouping multiple countries in similar “stage of
557 technology development” classes. However, for air quality modeling and exposure in major
558 cities the patterns in, and within, individual countries are important. This is illustrated with
559 diesel fuel in Argentina as an example (Table 7). Argentina has three grades of diesel.
560 Grade 1 (Agrodiesel or Gasoil Agro)) is intended mainly for agricultural equipment. Grade
561 2 (Gasoil Común; common diesel fuel) is intended for the bulk of diesel fuelled vehicles
562 and the sulphur limit of 500 ppm is not strictly enforced. Grade 3 diesel fuel, also known as
563 Gasoil Ultra, is the highest quality diesel fuel. Another complication is that a policy or
564 resolution may be accepted but the delay in implementation can be substantial; as seen in
565 Table 7; a resolution for low sulphur fuels was accepted in 2016 but availability on the
566 market is not expected until 3 years later. These kinds of details are important but often
567 only known by local or national experts. In the supplement material we provide additional
568 information on sulphur contents in fuel and its evolution in SA (see Table S2), illustrating
569 the importance of national and subnational policies. However, from **Table 7** we can already
570 see how challenging proper incorporation and spatial distribution will be for global
571 emission inventories. Various grades may exist next to each other and will be implemented
572 differently across the country, severely affecting the emissions in urban population centers.
573 The example of the complex temporal and spatial implementation of the sulphur fuel
574 standards shows the importance of working with local and national teams, especially when
575 high resolution and spatial distribution are important to predict exposure and define
576 mitigation measures. For global scale studies these details will be of limited importance but
577 when understanding the air pollution in South American cities or regions it may be crucial.
578 Also, when assessing climate impacts and mitigation options this may become increasingly
579 important.

580

581

Figure 8: Same as Figure 7 but for global inventory ECLIPSE.

582

Grade	name	Sulphur limit (ppm)				
		2006	2008	2009	Current	June 2016 ^{a)}
1	Agrodiesel or Gasoil Agro	3000	2500	2000	1500	1000
2	Gasoil Comun	1500 ^{b)} /250	1500 ^{b)} /2000	500 ^{b)} /2000	500	30
		0				
3	Gasoil Ultra	500	500	50	10	10

583

Table 7: Stepwise changes in diesel Sulphur limits in Argentina since 2006.

584

^{a)} Date of resolution, market availability is expected in 2019.

585 ^{b)} Sold in high population zones (more than 90,000 inhabitants, since 2008 50,000 inhabitants)

586

587 The analysis of local city emission estimates against results from global inventories
588 for the corresponding domain strongly highlight the importance of including local
589 information. The emission estimates are dramatically different. If emissions are to be
590 applied to forecast air quality and/or to develop mitigation measures the results from
591 downscaled global inventories as compared to local city data will be entirely different. In
592 order to come to more general conclusions we have calculated the ratio by source sector for
593 the downscaled emissions from the global inventories and the local city inventories (Table
594 8). In this table a value smaller than 1 indicates that the local estimate is higher (green
595 shading), a value higher than 1 indicates the downscaled estimate is higher (orange
596 shading). The industry and power sectors had to be grouped because in the city inventories
597 this is often one category. A comparison for total emissions could only be made for
598 Santiago and Buenos Aires because other city inventories are not complete. However, for
599 these two cities the sectors transportation, RCO and Industry and power represent $62 \pm 10\%$
600 and $79 \pm 9\%$ of the emissions for PM₁₀ and NO_x, respectively. Hence, the comparison of
601 the other cities is likely to cover at least the most important sectors and emissions.

602 Except Lima, for each global inventory the magnitude of the estimated emissions
603 between the two domains (large and small) is mostly different, yet the relative magnitude to
604 the local inventory is in general independent of the selected domain with the exception of
605 total NO_x Emissions in Buenos Aires from EDGAR, transport PM₁₀ emissions in Bogota
606 and NO_x emissions in Lima from ECLIPSE. Therefore, the following analysis will focus
607 on the dominant features between the local inventory and the equivalent estimate from each
608 global inventory.

609 The results show that transportation emissions are estimated to be higher in local city
610 inventories, except for Rio de Janeiro where global inventories are higher than the local
611 inventory. Sometimes the result is close to 1 (e.g. PM₁₀ ECLIPSE for Lima) but more
612 often the discrepancies are large, up to a factor of 5 (e.g. NO_x ECLIPSE for Santiago) or
613 even up to a factor of 10 when the NO_x ECLIPSE estimate for Lima based on the small
614 domain is considered. This is remarkable because the selected cities represent a large
615 fraction of the national population and transport emissions are assumed to be in some way

616 proportional to population, and in the case of Santiago 40% of the Chilean population lives
 617 in the Santiago Metropolitan region.

618

City	Inventory	Transport		Residential		Industry		Total	
		PM10	NOx	PM10	NOx	PM10	NOx	PM10	NOx
Bogota	Local	1 ^{a)}	1	NA ^{a)}	NA	1	1	NA	NA
	EDGAR-S	0.44	0.19			5.5	3.1		
	EDGAR-L	0.54	0.24			8.1	4.3		
	ECLIPSE-S	0.96	0.07			1.2	3.1		
	ECLIPSE-L	2.25	0.22			3.1	3.8		
Lima	Local	1	1	1	1	1	1	NA	NA
	EDGAR-S	0.30	0.52	49	5.4	8.7	32		
	EDGAR-L	0.35	0.60	50	5.6	8.7	32		
	ECLIPSE-S	1.1	0.17	76	8.2	14.2	39		
	ECLIPSE-L	1.1	0.17	76	8.2	14.2	39		
Rio de Janeiro*	Local	1	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	EDGAR-S	0.60	1.3						
	EDGAR-L	0.96	1.9						
	ECLIPSE-S	3.0	0.44						
	ECLIPSE-L	5.2	1.1						
Santiago	Local	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	EDGAR-S	0.21	0.33	13	2.5	18	3.1	9.2	0.79
	EDGAR-L	0.26	0.39	17	3.1	22	3.8	11	0.95
	ECLIPSE-S	1.4	0.31	10	2.0	7.3	9.8	6.0	1.6
	ECLIPSE-L	2.0	0.42	17	3.7	11	11	9.6	1.8
Buenos Aires	Local	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	EDGAR-S	0.13	0.25	6.2	3.2	32	12	4.1	0.97
	EDGAR-L	0.19	0.37	8.0	3.6	34	13	4.9	1.2
	ECLIPSE-S	2.6	0.50	13	1.7	8.9	6.7	3.8	0.83
	ECLIPSE-L	3.0	0.62	16	2.0	12	7.7	4.9	0.98

619

620 **Table 8:** Ratio of city domain inventory over local city inventory for PM10 and NOx emissions for transport,
 621 RCO and industry & power. A comparison of total emissions could only be done for Santiago and Buenos
 622 Aires.

623 ^{a)}NA = Not Available; A ratio of 1 for the local inventory indicates the source sector is estimated, if no sector
 624 estimate is available in the local inventory, a ratio for EDGAR or ECLIPSE could not be calculated.

625 *PM as TSP in local

626

627 In contrast to the emissions from the transportation sector, the emissions from other
 628 sectors (Residential and Industry & Power) are overwhelmingly larger in the downscaled
 629 global inventories. The discrepancies can easily amount to a factor 10 or more with an

630 extreme of a factor 70 for ECLIPSE PM10 from the Residential sector in Lima. An
631 overestimation in downscaled global inventories for RCO emissions is not surprising as
632 they are likely to use population density as a proxy, whereas national or cities information
633 may have better data on which fuels are used where in the country; e.g. more in rural or
634 colder mountainous areas. As a result the ratio for the total emission (Table 8, right
635 column) again comes closer to 1 but the unbalance in individual sectors suggests that this is
636 a case of a better fit for the wrong reasons. Moreover, for air quality modeling emission
637 height and emission timing, which vary by source sector, is important and for mitigation
638 measures the sector information is crucial. While we highlight that the local information is
639 crucial, it should be acknowledged that this is often lacking (only 2 cities provide a
640 complete inventory) and the use of downscaled global inventories is the only option. A
641 deeper understanding is further hampered by the scarcity of national total emission
642 inventories. For example, if the national total emission for transport between EDGAR or
643 ECLIPSE and a national inventory would be similar but the ratio for the major city would
644 be really different, we would know that this is due to spatial distribution and much less
645 likely a fundamental difference in activity and emission factors used. Hence, national
646 countrywide emission inventories are not only needed to model air quality on the national
647 scale but also to put city emissions in perspective. Such an analysis was made by Puliafito
648 et al. (2017) for Argentina by comparing their national inventory (GEAA) with EDGAR.
649 Although the estimated CO₂ emissions were very close (within 1%), large differences were
650 found for the air pollutants with the national inventory being 1.7, 1.1, and 1.4 higher for
651 NO_x, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} but only 0.4 times the EDGAR estimate for SO₂. In line with our
652 results in Table 8, the attribution to source sectors was often dramatically different partly
653 masking the difference in the totals. Moreover, Puliafito et al. (2017) conclude that the
654 spatial distribution by EDGAR was not adequate for Argentina, especially for transport and
655 residential sectors, leading to an overestimation in rural areas and an underestimation in
656 urban areas. We refer to Puliafito et al. (2017), for a more detailed analysis.

657 In addition to the differences of the fraction of national emissions allocated to the
658 different cities in the global inventories, we note that the spatial distribution of these
659 emissions vary largely not only between the inventories but also with respect to the
660 physical location of the actual city (Figure S12 and S13 in the supplement material). For

661 example, ECLIPSE locates most of the emissions of Santiago outside the city limits
662 extending even over the Andes to the border with Argentina. Similarly, although EDGAR
663 partially distributes the emissions within the city, they are centered on the northern border
664 and an important fraction is outside the city limits.

665

666 5 Conclusions

667

668 Air quality modeling and exposure assessment needs, next to a validated chemistry
669 transport model, two critical inputs; meteorological data and emissions data. National
670 emission inventories in South America have focused on GHG as part of their obligation to
671 the UNFCCC. Only for Argentina has a national emission inventory of air pollutants recently
672 been released (Castesana et al., 2018; Puliafito et al., 2015, 2017). Hence, studies assessing
673 air quality at national, regional or continental scales in SA have been relying on global
674 emission data sets. Several global emission inventories provide estimates for the selected
675 SA countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and Peru) for the past and present. These
676 have been compiled and compared here with a further analysis focusing on three recent
677 inventories (EDGAR 4.3.1, ECLIPSEv5, and CEDSv3) as they include data at least up to
678 2010 and can be compared with recent national or city scale emissions estimates.
679 Emissions from these global inventories are compared against available city-scale
680 inventories for a major city in each country by selecting the spatial domain from the
681 gridded data of the global inventory. Large discrepancies are found both between the global
682 datasets as well as when comparing downscaled global emissions data with local/national
683 city emissions data for the same domain. A direct conclusion of these discrepancies is that
684 it is not recommended to use a global emission inventory to derive city emission as input
685 for AQ modeling. The local situation does not appear to be properly represented and the
686 results of air quality modeling will depend significantly on the choice of inventory.
687 Moreover, a ranking of potential efficient mitigation measures would also depend on the
688 choice of emission inventory. Without more detailed national emissions data, a clear
689 conclusion on the origin of discrepancies cannot be made although we have given several
690 suggestions in the discussion. In some cases, it is clear that emission factors differ

691 substantially and this may need further attention in the future. At the same time, spatial
692 allocation can be another cause for large discrepancies. Simply said, the lack of consistent
693 national inventories prohibits further analysis. Efforts to create such national gridded
694 inventories in South America are urgently needed. Furthermore, source apportionment
695 studies would be an essential extension of analysis and therefore speciated atmospheric
696 measurements and chemical transport models with inventories are needed to get a better
697 understanding of emissions of various species within a given domain.

698 The emissions analyzed in this study, although limited to five countries out of the 12
699 existing countries in SA, are representative of most of the territory of South America as
700 well as most of its population. This study seeks to increase the understanding of strengths
701 and weaknesses of emissions data available for South America by focusing on these five
702 countries. The intention for the future is to include other countries not only from South
703 America but also Central America and the Caribbean.

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711

712 References

- 713 Alonso, M. F., Longo, K. M., Freitas, S. R., Mello da Fonseca, R., Marécal, V., Pirre, M.,
714 & Klenner, L. G. (2010). An urban emissions inventory for South America and its
715 application in numerical modeling of atmospheric chemical composition at local and
716 regional scales. *Atmospheric Environment*, 44(39), 5072–5083.
717 <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2010.09.013>.
- 718 Amann, M., et al. (2011), Cost-effective control of air quality and greenhouses gases in
719 Europe: Modeling and policy applications, *Environ. Modell. Softw.*, 26(12), 1489–1501,
720 doi:10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.07.012.
- 721 Amarante, V., M. Galván and X. Mancero (2016), "Inequality in Latin America: A global
722 measurement", *CEPAL Review*, vol. 2016/118, <https://doi.org/10.18356/a7337ed5-en>
- 723 Anenberg, S. C., Achakulwisut, P., Brauer, M., Moran, D., Apte, J. S. y Henze, D. K.:
724 Particulate matter-attributable mortality and relationships with carbon dioxide in 250

725 urban areas worldwide, *Sci. Rep.*, 9(1), 11552, doi:10.1038/s41598-019-48057-9, 2019.

726 Baumgardner, D., M. de Fatima Andrade, Z. Klimont, J. Kuylenstierna, S. M. Carvalho, N.

727 Borgford-Parnell, O. L. Mayol-Bracero, et al. “Short-Lived Climate Pollutants: Drivers,

728 Regional Emissions and Measurements.” In *Integrated Assessment of Short-Lived*

729 *Climate Pollutants in Latin America and the Caribbean: Improving Air Quality While*

730 *Contributing to Climate Change Mitigation*, 18–53. Paris: United Nations Environment

731 Programme (UNEP) and Climate and Clean Air Coalition (CCAC), 2018

732 Bond, T.C., E. Bhardwaj, R. Dong, R. Jogani, S. Jung, C. Roden, D.G. Streets, S.

733 Fernandes, and N. Trautmann, Historical emissions of black and organic carbon aerosol

734 from energy-related combustion, 1850-2000. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 21:

735 GB2018, doi:10.1029/2006GB002840, 2007.

736 Bond, T. C., et al. (2013), Bounding the role of black carbon in the climate system: A

737 scientific assessment, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 118(11), 5380–5552,

738 doi:10.1002/JGRD.50171.

739 Carpenter, A and Quispe-Agnoli, M. 2015. A Comparison of Economic and Social

740 Implications of Rapid Urbanization in Lima and Santiago de Chile. *Perspectives on*

741 *Global Development and Technology* 14(5): 497–518. DOI: 10.1163/15691497-

742 12341358

743 Castesana, Paula, Dawidowski, Laura, Finster, Laura, Gómez, Darío, & Taboada, Miguel.

744 (2018). Ammonia emissions from the agriculture sector in Argentina, 2000-2012.

745 *Atmospheric Environment*, 178C, 293–304.

746 CCAC-UNEP: Short-lived Climate Pollutants Short-lived Climate Pollutants in Latin

747 America, United Nations, Environmental Programme, Nairobi. Available from:

748 [https://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-](https://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean)

749 [pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean](https://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean), 2018.

750 Crippa, Monica Greet Janssens-Maenhout, Frank Dentener, Diego Guizzardi, Katerina

751 Sindelarova, Marilena Muntean, Rita Van Dingenen, Claire Granier: Forty years of

752 improvements in European air quality: regional policy-industry interactions with global

753 impacts, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16, 3825-3841, doi:10.5194/acp-16-3825-2016, 2016.

754 EDGAR website (<http://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

755 Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Muntean, M., Schaaf, E., Dentener, F., van Aardenne, J. A.,

756 Monni, S., Doering, U., Olivier, J. G. J., Pagliari, V., and Janssens-Maenhout, G.:

757 Gridded emissions of air pollutants for the period 1970–2012 within EDGAR v4.3.2,

758 *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 10, 1987-2013, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-1987-2018>, 2018

759 D’Angiola, A., Dawidowski, L., Gómez, D., and Osses, M. (2010). On-road traffic

760 emissions in a megacity. *Atmospheric Environment*, 44(4), 483–493.

761 Gallardo, L., Escribano, J., Dawidowski, L., Rojas, N., de Fátima Andrade, M., & Osses,

762 M. (2012). Evaluation of vehicle emission inventories for carbon monoxide and nitrogen

763 oxides for Bogotá, Buenos Aires, Santiago, and São Paulo. *Atmospheric Environment*,

764 47, 12–19. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.11.051>

765 Gallardo, L, Alonso, F, Andrade, MF, Barreto-Carvalho, V, Behrentz, E, et al. 2012a.
766 South American megacities. In: Zhu, T, Parrish, DD, Gauss, M, Doherty, S, Lawrence,
767 M, Gallardo, L and Kanakidou, M (eds.), *The Impacts of Megacities on Air Quality and*
768 *Climate Change: An IGAC Perspective* , 141–171. Geneva, Switzerland.

769 Garreaud, R. D., M. Vuille, R. Compagnucci, and J. Marengo (2009), Present-day South
770 American climate, *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.*, 281(3–4), 180–195,
771 doi:10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.10.032.

772 Gerência de Qualidade do Ar (GQA), Inventário, Emissões de Fontes Veiculares, Região
773 Metropolitana do Rio de Janeiro, Ano-Base 2013, Rio de Janeiro, 2016.

774 Gonzalez, C.M.; Gomez, C.D.; Rojas, N.Y.; Acevedo, H.; Aristizabal, B.H. (2017),
775 Relative impact of on-road vehicular and point-source industrial emissions of air
776 pollutants in a medium-sized Andean city. *Atmos. Environ.*, 152, 279–289.

777 Granier, C., Bessagnet, B., Bond, T., D’Angiola, A., Denier van der Gon, H., Frost, G. J.,
778 Heil, A., Kaiser, J. W., Kinne, S. , Klimont, Z., Kloster, S., Lamarque, J.-F., Liousse, C.,
779 Masui, T., Meleux, F., Mieville, A., Ohara, T., Raut, J.-C., Riahi, K., Schultz, M. G.,
780 Smith, S. J., Thompson, A., Aardenne, J., Werf, G. R. and Vuuren, D. P.: Evolution of
781 anthropogenic and biomass burning emissions of air pollutants at global and regional
782 scales during the 1980–2010 period, *Climatic Change*, 109(1–2), 163–190,
783 doi:10.1007/s10584-011-0154-1, 2011.

784 He, C., Ge, Y., Tan, C. M., Liu, Z., et al., "Emission Characteristics of a Heavy-Duty
785 Diesel Engine at Simulated High Altitudes," *Science of the Total Environment*, Vol.
786 409, pp. 3138-3143, 2011

787 Hoesly, R. M., Smith, S. J., Feng, L., Klimont, Z., Janssens-Maenhout, G., Pitkanen, T.,
788 Seibert, J. J., Vu, L., Andres, R. J., Bolt, R. M., Bond, T. C., Dawidowski, L., Kholod,
789 N., Kurokawa, J.-I., Li, M., Liu, L., Lu, Z., Moura, M. C. P., O’Rourke, P. R., and
790 Zhang, Q.: Historical (1750–2014) anthropogenic emissions of reactive gases and
791 aerosols from the Community Emissions Data System (CEDS), *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 11,
792 369–408, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-369-2018>, 2018.

793 HTAP: Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution 2010 – Part A: Ozone and Particulate
794 Matter, *Air Pollution Studies No. 17*, edited by: Dentener, F., Keating, T., and Akimoto,
795 H., United Nations, New York and Geneva, 2010.

796 Huang, Y. H. Shen, H. Chen, R. Wang, Y. Zhang, S. Su, Y. Chen, N. Lin, S. Zhuo, Q.
797 Zhong, X. Wang, J. Liu, B. Li, W. Liu, and S. Tao, Quantification of global primary
798 emissions of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and TSP from combustion and industrial process sources,
799 *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 48, 23, 13834–13843, 2014.

800 Infineum, Worldwide winter diesel fuel quality survey 2002, <http://www.infineum.com/>
801 Infineum Worldwide Winter Diesel Fuel Quality Survey 2014
802 Infineum Worldwide Winter Diesel Fuel Quality Survey 2016

803 IPCC, 2018: Summary for Policymakers. In: *Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special*
804 *Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related*
805 *global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global*

806 response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to
807 eradicate poverty [V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, H. O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P.
808 R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors, J. B. R.
809 Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M. I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, T.
810 Waterfield (eds.)]. World Meteorological Organization, Geneva, Switzerland, 32 pp
811 Janssens-Maenhout, G., Pagliari, V., Guizzardi, D., and Muntean, M.: Global emission
812 inventories in the Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) –
813 Manual (I): Gridding: EDGAR emissions distribution on global gridmaps, JRC Report,
814 EUR 25785 EN, ISBN 978-92-79-28283-6, doi:10.2788/81454, 2013.

815 Janssens-Maenhout, G., Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Dentener, F., Muntean, M., Pouliot, G.,
816 Keating, T., Zhang, Q., Kurokawa, J., Wankmüller, R., Denier van der Gon, H., Kuenen,
817 J. J. P., Klimont, Z., Frost, G., Darras, S., Koffi, B., and Li, M.: HTAP_v2.2: a mosaic of
818 regional and global emission grid maps for 2008 and 2010 to study hemispheric
819 transport of air pollution, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15, 11411-11432, doi:10.5194/acp-15-
820 11411-2015, 2015.

821 Janssens-Maenhout, G., Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Muntean, M., Schaaf, E., Dentener, F.,
822 Bergamaschi, P., Pagliari, V., Olivier, J. G. J., Peters, J. A. H. W., van Aardenne, J. A.,
823 Monni, S., Doering, U., and Petrescu, A. M. R.: EDGAR v4.3.2 Global Atlas of the
824 three major Greenhouse Gas Emissions for the period 1970–2012, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*
825 *Discuss.*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2017-79>, 2017.

826 Junker, C. and Liousse, C.: A global emission inventory of carbonaceous aerosol from
827 historic records of fossil fuel and biofuel consumption for the period 1860-1997, *Atmos.*
828 *Chem. Phys.*, 8, 1195-1207, doi:10.5194/acp-8-1195-2008, 2008.

829 Klimont, Z., Kupiainen, K., Heyes, C., Purohit, P., Cofala, J., Rafaj, P., Borken-Kleefeld,
830 J., and Schöpp, W.: Global anthropogenic emissions of particulate matter including
831 black carbon, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17, 8681-8723, [https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017)
832 2017, 2017.

833 Kumar Rodrigo and Belalcázar, Luis Carlos and Roja, Néstor Y., A. and J. (2016).
834 Application of WRF-Chem Model to Simulate PM10 Concentration over Bogota.
835 Aerosol and Air Quality Research, 16(5), 1206–1221.
836 <http://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.2015.05.0318>

837 Lamarque, JF et al. Historical (1850-2000) gridded anthropogenic and biomass burning
838 emissions of reactive gases and aerosols: methodology and application, *Atmospheric*
839 *Chemistry and Physics*, 2010 (ACP-2010-67) UNdata, United Nations Statistics
840 Division, <http://data.un.org/>, accessed June 2017

841 Longo, K. M., Freitas, S. R., Pirre, M., Marécal, V., Rodrigues, L. F., Panetta, J., ... Bela,
842 M. (2013). The Chemistry CATT-BRAMS model (CCATT-BRAMS 4.5): a regional
843 atmospheric model system for integrated air quality and weather forecasting and
844 research. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 6(5), 1389–1405. [http://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-1389-](http://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-1389-2013)
845 [2013](http://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-1389-2013)

846 Mazzeo, A., Huneus, N., Ordoñez, C., Orfanos-Cheuquelaf, A., Menut, L., Mailler, S.,
847 Valari, M., Denier van der Gon, H., Gallardo, L., Muñoz, R., Donoso, R., Galleguillos,
848 M., Osses, M., and Tolvett, S., (2018). Impact of residential combustion and transport
849 emissions on air pollution in Santiago during winter. *Atmospheric Environment*, 190,
850 195–208. <http://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.06.043>

851 Melamed, M. L., Schmale, J., & von Schneidmesser, E. (2016). Sustainable policy—key
852 considerations for air quality and climate change. *Current Opinion in Environmental*
853 *Sustainability*, 23, 85–91. <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2016.12.003>

854 Monks, P. S., Archibald, A. T., Colette, A., Cooper, O., Coyle, M., Derwent, R., ...
855 Williams, M. L. (2015). Tropospheric ozone and its precursors from the urban to the
856 global scale from air quality to short-lived climate forcer. *Atmospheric Chemistry and*
857 *Physics*, 15(15), 8889–8973. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-8889-2015>.

858 Ni, H., Zhao, W., Liu, L., Li, M., Fu, T. and Wang, Y., "A research of the effects of altitude
859 on the emissions and fuel consumption of a gasoline vehicle", 2014, *Automotive*
860 *Engineering* 36(10):1205-1209 and 1179.

861 Reis, S., P. Grennfelt, Z. Klimont, M. Amann, H. ApSimon, J.-P. Hettelingh, M. Holland,
862 et al. "From Acid Rain to Climate Change." *Science* 338, no. 6111 (November 30,
863 2012): 1153–54. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1226514>

864 Pachón, J., Galvis, B, Lombana, O., Carmona, L., Fajardo, S., Rincón, A., Meneses,
865 S., Chaparro, R., Nedbor-Gross, R., Henderson, B., 2018, Development and evaluation
866 of a comprehensive atmospheric emission inventory for air quality modeling in the
867 megacity of Bogotá, *Atmosphere*, 9 (2) (2018), p. 49, 10.3390/atmos9020049.

868 PNUD. 2017. *Desiguales: Orígenes, cambios y desafíos de la brecha social en Chile*.
869 Santiago, Chile: Ograma Impresores , 411. 978-956-7469-86-4. Available at:
870 <https://www.desiguales.org/>.

871 Puliafito, S. Enrique; Allende, David G., Castesana, Paula S., Ruggeri, María F. (2017):
872 High-resolution atmospheric emission inventory of the argentine energy sector.
873 Comparison with Edgar global emission database. *Heliyon* 3, e00489.
874 <http://doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2017.e00489>

875 Puliafito, S.E., Allende, D., Pinto, S., Castesana, P. (2015): High resolution inventory of
876 GHG emissions of the road transport sector in Argentina, *Atmospheric Environment*
877 101, 303-311. <http://doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.11.040>

878 Reátegui, W., Sánchez-Ccoyllo, O., Andrade, M., & Moya, A. (2018). PM2.5 Estimation
879 with the WRF/Chem Model, Produced by Vehicular Flow in the Lima Metropolitan
880 Area. *Open Journal of Air Pollution*, 215-243.

881 Riahi, K., Grübler, A., & Nakicenovic, N. (2007). Scenarios of long-term socio-economic
882 and environmental development under climate stabilization. *Technological Forecasting*
883 *and Social Change*, 74(7), 887–935.
884 <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2006.05.026>

885 Rojas, N.Y., Peñaloza, N.E.. Desagregación de inventarios de emisiones. Bogotá como caso
886 de estudio. Editorial Académica Española (2012-05-02). ISBN: 978-3-659-00796-5.

887 Rondanelli, R., Molina, A., and Falvey, M. (2015). The Atacama Surface Solar Maximum.
888 Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society, 96(3), 405–418.
889 <http://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00175.1>.

890 Rosário, N. E., K. M. Longo, S. R. Freitas, M. A. Yamasoe, and R. M. Fonseca. 2013.
891 "Modeling the South American regional smoke plume: aerosol optical depth variability
892 and surface shortwave flux perturbation." *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, **13** (6): 2923-2938
893 [10.5194/acp-13-2923-2013].

894 Saide, P.E., Mena-Carrasco, M., Tolvett, S., Hernandez, P., Carmichael, G.R., 2016. Air
895 quality forecasting for winter-time PM2.5 episodes occurring in multiple cities in central
896 and southern Chile. *J. Geophys. Res.: Atmosphere* 121 (1), 558–575.

897 Schneidmesser, Erika von, Paul S. Monks, James D. Allan, Lori Bruhwiler, Piers Forster,
898 David Fowler, Axel Lauer, et al. "Chemistry and the Linkages between Air Quality and
899 Climate Change." *Chemical Reviews* 115, no. 10 (May 27, 2015): 3856–97.
900 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00089>

901 Schmale, J., Shindell, D., Von Schneidmesser, E., Chabay, I., and Lawrence, M. (2014).
902 Air pollution: Clean up our skies. *Nature* 515, 335–337. doi:10.1038/515335a.

903 Schultz, M., S. Rast, M. van het Bolscher, T. Pulles, R. Brand, J. Pereira, B. Mota, A.
904 Spessa, S. Dalsøren, T. van Noije, S. Szopa, Emission data sets and methodologies for
905 estimating emissions, Report of the RETRO European project, EU-Contract No. EVK2-
906 CT-2002-00170, available at: [http://retro-archive.iek.fz-](http://retro-archive.iek.fz-juelich.de/data/documents/reports/)
907 [juelich.de/data/documents/reports/](http://retro-archive.iek.fz-juelich.de/data/documents/reports/), 2007.

908 Steffen W, Richardson K, Rockström J, Cornell SE, Fetzer I, et al. 2015. Planetary
909 boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science* 347(6223):
910 1259855.

911 Stohl, A., Aamaas, B., Amann, M., Baker, L. H., Bellouin, N., Berntsen, T. K., Boucher,
912 O., Cherian, R., Collins, W., Daskalakis, N., Dusinska, M., Eckhardt, S.,
913 Fuglestvedt, J. S., Harju, M., Heyes, C., Hodnebrog, Ø., Hao, J., Im, U., Kanakidou,
914 M., Klimont, Z., Kupiainen, K., Law, K. S., Lund, M. T., Maas, R., MacIntosh, C.
915 R., Myhre, G., Myriokefalitakis, S., Olivie, D., Quaas, J., Quennehen, B., Raut, J.-
916 C., Rumbold, S. T., Samset, B. H., Schulz, M., Seland, Ø., Shine, K. P., Skeie, R.
917 B., Wang, S., Yttri, K. E., and Zhu, T.: Evaluating the climate and air quality
918 impacts of short-lived pollutants, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15, 10529-10566,
919 doi:10.5194/acp-15-10529-2015, 2015.

920 Szedlmayer, M. and Kweon, C., "Effect of Altitude Conditions on Combustion and
921 Performance of a Multi-Cylinder Turbocharged Direct-Injection Diesel Engine," SAE
922 Technical Paper 2016-01-0742, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.4271/2016-01-0742>.

923 United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2018).
924 World Urbanization Prospects: The 2018 Revision, custom data acquired via website.
925 Available at <https://population.un.org/wup/Download/>

926 UNEP, Status of Fuel Quality and Vehicle Emission Standards Latin America and the
927 Caribbean, 2016

928 [http://staging.unep.org/transport/New/PCFV/pdf/Maps_Matrices/LAC/matrix/LAC_Fue](http://staging.unep.org/transport/New/PCFV/pdf/Maps_Matrices/LAC/matrix/LAC_FuelsVeh_November2016.pdf)
929 [lsVeh_November2016.pdf](http://staging.unep.org/transport/New/PCFV/pdf/Maps_Matrices/LAC/matrix/LAC_FuelsVeh_November2016.pdf) accessed April 2017

930 UNEP/CCAC (2018). Integrated Assessment of Short-Lived Climate Pollutants in Latin
931 America and the Caribbean: Improving Air Quality While Contributing to Climate
932 Change Mitigation, Paris: United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and
933 Climate and Clean Air Coalition (CCAC);
934 [http://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-](http://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean)
935 [pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean](http://ccacoalition.org/en/resources/integrated-assessment-short-lived-climate-pollutants-latin-america-and-caribbean)

936 USACH, 2014. Informe final: Actualizacion y sistematizacion del inventario de emisiones
937 de contaminantes atmosféricos en la region metropolitana. Universidad de Santiago de
938 Chile.^[1]_{SEP}

939 van Vuuren, D.P., J. Edmonds, M. Kainuma, K. Riahi, A. Thomson, K. Hibbard, G.C.
940 Hurtt, T. Kram, V. Krey, J.-F. Lamarque, T. Masui, M. Meinshausen, N. Nakicenovic,
941 S.J. Smith, and S.K. Rose, The representative concentration pathways: an overview,
942 Climatic Change, 109, 5-31, DOI: 10.1007/s10584-011-0148-z, 2011.

943 Vivanco, M.G., Andrade, M.F., 2006. Validation of the emission inventory in the São
944 Paulo metropolitan area of Brazil based on ambient concentrations ratios of CO, NMOG
945 and NOx and on a photochemical model. Atmospheric Environment 40,1189 – 1198.

946 Wang, H., Ge, Y., Hao, L., Xu, X., Tan, J., Li, J., Wu, L., Yang, J., Yang, D., Peng, J.,
947 Yang, J., Yang, R., 2018, The real driving emission characteristics of light-duty diesel
948 vehicle at various altitudes, Atmos. Env., 191, 126-131.
949 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.07.060>

950 WHO (World Health Organization), 2017, Evolution of WHO air quality guidelines: past,
951 present and future (2017), vi + 32 pages, ISBN 978 92 890 5230 6

952 World bank, World Development Indicators, 2017, accessed June 6, 2017.
953 <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL>,
954
955
956
957
958
959
960